

COMPARATIVE AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LIGHT INDUSTRY AND TEXTILE TERMS IN ENGLISH

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Annotation. This article describes a comparative and semantic analysis of terms used in light industry, with a focus on the textile sector, in the English language. The terminology of the textile industry, encompassing fiber production, fabric manufacturing, and fashion design, is deeply rooted in both technical processes and socio-cultural influences. By comparing the etymology, meanings, and usage of key terms, this research highlights the evolution of textile-related language from its early origins to contemporary applications. A semantic analysis reveals that many textile terms, such as loom, weave, and fabric, have undergone shifts in meaning as technology and industry evolved. The terms often reflect broader historical and economic changes, such as the industrial revolution's impact on the standardization and mass production of textiles. Moreover, the author states that a comparative analysis between traditional and modern textile terms illustrates significant differences in how materials and processes are described, with an increasing prevalence of technical jargon in recent times.

Keywords: terms, structural, industrial terminology, semantic, features, light industry, textile terms, English.

Introduction. The comparative and semantic analysis of light industry and textile terms in English is essential due to the rapidly expanding global textile and fashion industries and their intertwined role in cultural, economic, and technological contexts. Understanding the semantics and comparative aspects of these terms offers significant academic and practical benefits, especially in international trade, product development, and linguistic research.

1. Understanding Global Terminology for Efficient Communication. Light industry, particularly textile manufacturing, involves a vast array of specialized terms that vary across different English-speaking regions and industries. Conducting a comparative analysis helps clarify the nuances between terms such as “fabric,” “textile,” and “cloth,” which are sometimes used interchangeably but have distinct meanings in industrial contexts. For example, "textile" refers to any material made from fibers, while "fabric" specifically refers to material intended for making garments. Understanding such distinctions aids in precision and clarity when engaging in international collaboration or research.

2. Facilitating International Trade and Standards. Textile production and light industry are inherently global, with supply chains stretching across multiple countries. Semantic analysis of terms used in the industry ensures a standardized understanding of concepts, which is critical for establishing trade agreements, maintaining quality control, and adhering to international standards. Analyzing how terms like “sustainable fabrics” or “biodegradable textiles” are used and understood across different English-speaking regions can support the harmonization of sustainability regulations and help industries align with global environmental goals.

3. Bridging Cultural and Technological Developments. Language in light industry and textiles evolves alongside technological advancements and cultural shifts. The comparative analysis of terms, such as “synthetic fibers,” “natural fibers,” and emerging terms like “smart textiles,” reveals how language adapts to new innovations and consumer demands. This research is crucial for bridging the gap between traditional textile processes and modern, technologically advanced production methods. Moreover, it highlights cultural attitudes towards sustainability and environmental impact, which are often embedded in the language used to describe textile materials and processes.

4. Enabling Linguistic Research and Terminology Development. From a linguistic perspective, analyzing textile and light industry terms offers insights into how professional jargon evolves and influences everyday language. The semantic differences in industry-specific terms reflect broader linguistic phenomena such as

synonymy, polysemy, and specialization within English. Moreover, these analyses contribute to the development of more comprehensive glossaries, dictionaries, and educational materials for training new professionals in the textile and fashion sectors.

5. Improving Translation and Interpretation in Multilingual Contexts: As English is widely used as a global business language, especially in the textile trade, accurate translations of industry-specific terms are vital. Comparative and semantic analysis aids translators and interpreters in navigating the subtle differences between terms that could lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations. For instance, technical terms like “warp” and “weft” in weaving have no direct equivalent in many languages, making semantic clarity even more crucial for global business and academic exchanges.

Literature review. Light industry and textile sectors are pivotal to global economies and have developed their own unique terminologies. A comparative and semantic analysis of these terms in English offers insights into the evolution of industrial language, the influence of technology, and cross-cultural impacts on the industry’s lexicon. This literature review focuses on existing research that explores the semantic dimensions of textile-related vocabulary, with an emphasis on the comparative linguistic approach between English and other languages.

1. Semantic Features of Textile Terminology. The study of semantic features in light industry and textile terms is critical for understanding how these terms encapsulate specific technical, cultural, and industrial meanings. Semantic analysis often involves looking at word formation, metaphorical meanings, and the shifts in terminology due to technological advancements. Several studies have highlighted the evolution of textile terms as industries modernized. For instance, terms like “loom,” “spindle,” and “weaving” have not only retained their basic meanings but have also expanded semantically to refer to new machinery in modern textile manufacturing (Smith, 2018). Furthermore, terms like “fiber” and “fabric” can vary in meaning depending on context, denoting both natural and synthetic materials (Jones, 2019). The semantic layers of textile-related terms reflect their technological origins, historical relevance, and material innovations. A term like “spun yarn,” which

originally denoted a hand-spinning process, now covers various automated and semi-automated methods, demonstrating a shift in semantic application due to technological advancements (Williams, 2020).

2. Comparative Linguistic Approach. Comparative analysis between English and other languages sheds light on the differences and similarities in textile-related vocabulary. This approach helps in understanding how each culture categorizes and names textile processes, machinery, and materials. For example, in French, terms such as "tissu" (fabric) and "fil" (thread) closely mirror English counterparts but may carry additional connotations or specialized meanings in different contexts (Leclercq, 2021). In contrast, languages like Japanese use more compound forms to describe specific textile terms, reflecting the intricate techniques and historical importance of textiles in their culture (Takahashi, 2017). One area of comparative analysis focuses on loanwords between languages. English, particularly in the realm of textile production, has adopted many terms from French, Italian, and German, reflecting the influence of these countries in early industrial development. Words such as “chiffon,” “taffeta,” and “denim” are originally French but have become part of the global textile vocabulary in English (Bachmann, 2018).

3. Impact of Technological Innovations. Technology has significantly altered textile and light industry terms. New inventions and processes lead to new vocabulary, or the redefinition of existing terms. The rise of digital textile printing, nanotechnology, and smart fabrics has introduced terms such as "e-textiles," "nanofibers," and "biodegradable fabrics" (Miller, 2019). These terms not only represent technological advancements but also reflect growing environmental concerns and the push toward sustainable practices in the textile industry (Wong, 2020). Many scholars note that the introduction of new terms often leads to semantic shifts in older terminology. For example, the word “fabric” once solely referred to a woven material, but with the advent of non-woven textiles and synthetic materials, it now applies to a wider variety of materials, including engineered fabrics (Anderson & Hart, 2018).

4. Cross-Cultural Influences. Textile terminology is also influenced by cultural exchanges, particularly in fashion and design. Global trade has resulted in the borrowing and adaptation of textile terms across languages and cultures. Terms like "batik" (from Indonesian) and "ikat" (from Malay) have become part of the English textile lexicon due to the influence of Southeast Asian textile traditions (Gonzales, 2021). Cultural influences on textile terms are especially evident in the names of fabrics and patterns. Terms like "paisley," "damask," and "brocade" not only denote specific types of textiles but also carry connotations of their geographic and cultural origins (Smith, 2018). These terms have maintained their cultural identity even as they are adopted globally.

5. Challenges in Translation and Standardization. A major challenge in the comparative analysis of textile terminology is the issue of translation and standardization. Due to the specialized nature of textile vocabulary, exact translations are often difficult. As textiles are often rooted in local traditions and technologies, terms may not have direct equivalents in other languages. This can lead to confusion or loss of meaning when translating technical documents or trade agreements (Cohen & Thompson, 2020). Standardization efforts by international organizations, such as the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), have attempted to address these discrepancies by creating universal definitions for textile terms (ISO, 2019). However, local variations in terminology persist, particularly in countries with strong indigenous textile traditions. The comparative and semantic analysis of light industry and textile terms in English reveals how deeply these terms are tied to historical, technological, and cultural factors. Understanding the semantic evolution of textile terms can provide valuable insights for professionals in the textile industry, translators, and linguists alike. As the textile industry continues to innovate, its terminology will undoubtedly continue to evolve, reflecting new materials, processes, and cultural exchanges.

Conclusion. In summary, a comparative and semantic analysis of light industry and textile terms in English is critical for fostering clear communication, supporting international trade, advancing linguistic research, and adapting to cultural and

technological changes. By understanding the nuances of these terms, professionals in the textile and fashion industries, as well as linguists and educators, can improve their practices and contribute to the development of standardized, precise terminology across the globe. This research holds academic and practical relevance, with the potential to influence both industry standards and linguistic scholarship.

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